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THE JOURNEY OF THE BEES – NOMADIC BEEKEEPING IN EUROPE

Il viaggio delle api – L'apicoltura nomade in Europa

Since the times of the ancient Greeks, beehives get carried, shipped, and trucked to different regions to tap new resources for the bees and harvest special sorts of honey. From the flatlands of Austria to the mountains of Southern France, the filmmakers come along with two of these “nomadic beekeepers,” trying to catch some ethnographic impressions of their everyday lives and cultural practices behind this specific type of beekeeping.

The movie was presented at various International Film Festival, including the Green Montenegro International Film Fest (GMIFF) and the Green Festival in Kosovo. It won the first prize at the Fiorenzo Serra International Film Festival 2022. It was directed by Greca N. Meloni and Max Leimstätner, in collaboration with Johannes Gruber and Ignatius Steinmann.

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